

Comparative Study of Chromium (VI) Removal by Activated Neem leave Powder and Neem Saw Dust : Isotherms & Kinetics

Radharani Das^{*a}, Anima Das^b, Ishita Sinha^c, Kumar Kaustav^a

^aDepartment of Chemical Engg, Haldia institute of technology, Haldia -721657, India

^bDepartment of Chemical Engg, Meghnath Saha Institute of Technology, Haldia

^c Associate Manager , Linde India Limited., Kolkata

Email Corresponding Author : radha.das6@gmail.com,

Abstract: Effluents from various industries like electroplating, leather tanning, cement, petrochemicals, dye etc, contains significant amount of toxic hexavalent chromium, Cr(VI) with concentration of 10th to 100th ppm level. To avoid the health hazard from long term exposure of Cr(VI), there is high demand of feasible cost effective technologies which would eventually save aquatic & human lives from the carcinogenic effect of Cr⁺⁶. In this work activated Neem leaf powder (NLP) and Neem saw dust (NSD) were selected as cost effective adsorbent for elimination of chromium (VI) compound from synthetic waste water using adsorption process at various pH, concentration, time and temperature. It was observed that the reduction of Cr⁺⁶ increases with the increase of time of contact and adsorbent amount but decreases with higher solute concentration. Determination of free Cr⁺⁶ ions concentration in the effluent has been determined Spectro-Photometrically at 542 nm wavelength. The results show that 98 - 99.88 % reduction of Cr⁺⁶ may be achieved successfully depending on pH and nature of adsorbents, temperature and concentration of solution. The rate constants of these sorption processes were observed using pseudo first order and pseudo second order reaction kinetic models. Freundlich Isotherm and rearranged Langmuir model were used to find out the applicability of these isotherms for both adsorption processes. Results also show that the performance efficiency of activated NLP was slightly higher compared to the NSD at the same sorption conditions. The maximum adsorption of Cr(VI) was obtained as 55.86 and 40.0 mg/gm using NLP and NSD respectively.

Key Words: Hexavalent Chromium, Adsorption Kinetics, Isotherms, Neem leaf powder, Neem Saw Dust

1. Introduction :

With the increasing population and human demand civilisation and industrialization are growing very rapidly. As a result, polluted contaminated waste water discharge from various industries into the water are increasing rapidly and becoming the potential threat by affecting the surface water. Chromium is a highly carcinogenic, corrosion resistance and hazardous metal which usually generates from steel fabrication, textile, leather and paints any many other industries. Due to high toxicity Cr⁺⁶ is highly hazardous, and it causes serious effects like irritation of the skin^[12], Lung Cancer, stomach cancer, chronic bronchitis, headache, and also has an opposing potential to modify the DNA transcription process^[3].

As per the Indian standards the allowable limit for Cr⁺⁶ for public sewage is 2.00 mg/l^[4], for effluent release into surface water is 0.10 mg/l and potable drinking water is 0.05mg/l. But the concentrations range of Cr⁺⁶ in the industrial effluent usually much higher compared to the allowable limit. Many treatment methods like Ion exchange, adsorption and chemical precipitation are available for reduction of toxicity level from the waste water^[5]. Among all these process bio-adsorption process is highly cost effective, eco-friendly, efficient

reliable well acknowledged process for removal of trace elements from waste water. A variety of bio-adsorbents are used by various researchers for successful removal of toxic metals from the waste water before their disposal in to the environment [6, 15, 23].

Singh et. al [7] studied the influence of different parameters like, pH, adsorbent dosage, contact time, initial solute concentration, temperature using mangiferaindica bark. They achieved 80.2 % removal of Cr^{+6} from solution consisting 50 mg/l Cr^{+6} at pH 2. Smita M, et.al [8] studied the efficiency of the activated sugarcane bagasse at various agitation time, solute concentration, and pH and reported 96.1% removal of Cr^{+6} . Effect of pH, particle size, contact time and adsorbent doses on Cr^{+6} removal was observed by S. Dhana kumar et .al. [9] using treated cooked tea dust. They obtained 90% removal at optimum pH of 2.

Bio-sorptive behaviour of spent tea leaves for adsorption of Cr^{+6} from tannery waste water and the influence of independent parameters like contact time, adsorbent amount, contact time and pH was also studied by Alam et al. [10]. They found 95.4% removal of solute using 14.0 g/L adsorbent dose and achieved optimum sorption capacity of 10.6 mg/g at pH of 10.0. Anand S A et.al achieved 90 % reduction of Cr^{+6} [11] using rice husk ash as an adsorbent from the synthetic solution. Maize bran, an agricultural waste was taken by S.H. Hasan et.al [12] for removal of Cr^{+6} from aqueous solutions and reported that this adsorption is mono layer in nature and effective at higher temperature and lower pH range. Zainul Akmar Zakaria et.al [13] studied the adsorption characteristics of untreated rubber wood sawdust (RWS) for removal of Cr(VI) and found the optimum removal about 100% at pH less than 2. R. Gayathri et.al [14] observed the capacity of tamarind seeds, a low cost adsorbent and achieved 80% removal of Cr^{+6} . They reported that the maximum monolayer adsorption of Cr(VI) on tamarind seeds was obtained as 29.41 mg/g at pH 2 in equilibrium time of 240 min.

Adsorption capacity of powder Papaya Seeds (PPS) for removal of Cr^{+6} and the influence of various physico-chemical parameters like adsorbent dosage, initial metal ion concentration, pH, particle size of adsorbent and agitation time, has been done by Hema Krishna R et al [15]. Kinetic studies confirmed the suitability of the pseudo first order model. Tuama et al studied to find out the efficiency of Tobacco leaves for removal of Cr^{+6} from water solution [16]. Influence of various sorption parameters for reduction of Cr^{+6} was studied by Ba et al [17] using olive wastes derived carbon in a batch process. They showed that the maximum sorption capacity of the developed carbon for Cr^{+6} was 74.9 mg/g at pH 2.0 and Cr^{+3} was 14.3 mg/g at 9.0. Their experimental finding and kinetic studies confirm that this sorption process follows pseudo-second-order kinetic, Langmuir isotherm model, exothermic and spontaneous in nature.

Raw macadamia nutshell powder and chemically modified macadamia nutshell were selected as adsorbent of Cr^{+6} by Pakade et al. [18]. They suggested the optimum adsorption conditions are pH 2.0, adsorbent dose of 0.2 g and initial solute concentration of 100 mg/l.

The maximum elimination of Cr^{+6} from wastewater was found as 99.0 % using Almond green hull powder by Nasseh et al. [19]. They suggested that the optimum elimination of Cr(VI) significantly depends on acidic medium, solute concentration and temperature. Satish et al [20] studied the effect of adsorbent particle size and pH for decontamination of Cr^{+6} from synthetic waste water using mangrove leaf powder and suggested that optimum particle size and solution pH are 0.5 mm and 2.0 respectively for better performance. They also proposed that the process is endothermic and spontaneous in nature. Dula et.al. [21] achieved 98.3%

Cr^{+6} removal and 59.2 mg/g adsorption capacity at 27 °C and pH 2.0 using activated carbon

produced from bamboo waste . Sunil et al^[22] selected groundnut shell powder, activated charcoal and activated neem leaf powder, for removal of Cr⁺⁶ from the waste water . They achieved up to 69.0%, 87.3% and 95.7% elimination of Cr⁺ using groundnut shell powder , neem leaf powder and modified neem leaf powder respectively.

B.V.Babu et. al ^[24] and M. Venkateswara Rao et.al^[4] also investigated the potentiality of the neem leaf powder for elimination of Cr⁺⁶ from dilute solution . Maximum adsorption capacity of the NLP was found as 62.97 mg/gm at pH by Babu et al . Rao et all achieved 90% removal of hexavalent chromium. They also suggested that the adsorption follow pseudo second order kinetics.

In this paper, indigenously developed activated NLP and NSD were used as natural adsorbents to eliminate the toxicity level of the hexavalent chromium (Cr⁺⁶). Effect of various parameters like contact time, pH, adsorbent amount, initial solute concentration and temperature on reduction of Cr⁺⁶ from its synthetic solution has been studied extensively . Attempt has been taken to find out the adsorption isotherms and kinetics at different sorption conditions .

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Adsorbent preparation

Neem leaves and Neem sawdust were collected from campus of the Institute and local saw mill. Those materials were washed several times to remove the impurities and dark green or brown color, dried at room temperature , grounded to fine powder, sieved to 250-350 μm and activated the adsorbents by boiling followed by acidification . The residue kept at room temperature for drying followed by heating at 100 – 120 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 3 to 4 hrs to make the adsorbent moisture free completely and collected safely. Laboratory grade HCl , NaOH and K₂Cr₂O₇ (Fisher Scientific, Kolkata) was used in this experiment.

2.2. Adsorption studies

Batch adsorption were carried out using 0.20 to 1.0gm/l of activated NLP and NSD as adsorbent for elimination of Cr⁺⁶ from synthetic solution having concentration of 10 to 100 mg/l using magnetic stirrer with rpm of 300-350 and pH of 1.35. Kinetic studies were done at 304 K, 313K and 323K. The solute concentration left in supernatant solutions after sorption were found using a UV-vis spectrophotometer (Simazu-1800) at wave length of 542 nm and various time intervals up to 300 min. The influence of various parameters like pH , adsorbent amount, solute concentration and temperature on removal efficiency were performed at various conditions.

3.0 Characterization of Adsorbents

3.1 SEM analysis

Characterization of the neem Leaf powder (NLP) and neem saw dust (NSD) for determination of surface morphology has been done by SEM (Zeiss EVO 10, U.K.) studies and XRD analysis and reported elsewhere ^[25] . It was noted that the neem leaf powder was an assemblage of fine irregular spherical particles with maximum particle size of 10 μm in diameter. But the NSD surface have uneven surface morphology having fibrous structure with asymmetrical macro-pores and cavities. Similar studies were done by Arif et al and Kibami, et al., 2017 ^[26, 27] also reported earlier ^[25].

Fig. 1. SEM images of adsorbent: (a) Neem leaf powder and (b) Neem Saw dust showing the surface morphology of the adsorbents

3.2 FTIR analysis

Due to presence of carboxylic acid groups a broad peak at $3590\text{-}2550\text{ cm}^{-1}$ for the O-H stretching vibration was found in the IR-bands (Fig. 2.) . The C=O stretching near $1765\text{-}1725\text{ cm}^{-1}$ was observed for the presence of acid anhydrides . Benzene ring stretching show the corresponding bands at $1615\text{-}1590\text{ cm}^{-1}$. Presence of NO_2 compounds due to asymmetric stretching was noted with the bands at $1575\text{-}1545\text{ cm}^{-1}$. The contribution of O-H in carboxylic acid groups and COO-stretching show the bands at $1440\text{-}1400\text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $1400\text{-}1310\text{ cm}^{-1}$ respectively.

Fig. 2. Analysis of Neem leaf powder (NLP) using FTIR at high frequency region, (reported in our earlier work [25])

4.0 The influence of various operating parameters on the removal of Cr^{+6}

4.1 Influence of adsorbent amount and contact time :

Figure 3. show the influence of adsorbent amount and time of contact on reduction of Cr^{+6} . It shows that the equilibrium concentration may be achieved at about 240 min. Results also imply that the reduction of Cr^{+6} depends on dosing amount . With the increase of NLP amount from 0.3 gm/l to 1.0 gm/l removal increases from 88.6% to 99.88% at the pH of 1.35 . The same nature of reduction also observed for NSD also in Fig. 3b . It show that the reduction of Cr^{+6} increases from 77.58 to 99.28% for increase of same amount dosing. The findings of other investigators also agree with these results [15, 22, 25] . The results suggest that the reduction of

solute takes place due to increase of surface area on the adsorbent. The fig 3 also shows that the adsorption capacity of activated NLP is slightly higher than that of NSD at same operating condition.

Fig 3.: Effect of amount of adsorbent (a) NLP and (b) NSD on removal of Cr^{+6} (Cr^{+6} : 10 mg/l, temp: 30° C, pH 1.35)

4.2 Influence of solute concentrations on removal of Chromium.

Fig. 4 show the effect of initial concentration of Cr^{+6} in the solution on its removal by the adsorbents. It was noted that with the change of solute concentration from 10 to 50 mg/l, the removal quantity of Cr^{+6} decreases from 99.88 to 77.82 % and 98.68 to 48.68 % for NLP and NSD respectively. This is because the availability of surface area on adsorbent will be higher at lower solute concentration. But at higher solute concentration vacant spaces are unavailable after monolayer formation on the adsorbent. Similar sorption behavior was suggested by other investigators also [19, 20, 25].

Fig 4.: Effect of solute concentration on reduction of Cr^{+6} using different adsorbent (a) NLP and (b) NSD (Adsorbent : 0.5 gm/l, Temp: 30° C, pH 1.35)

4.3 Influence of pH on the adsorption process

Reduction performance of Cr^{+6} at various pH on different adsorbents has been described in the Fig. 5. It shows that with decrease of pH from 3.36 to 1.35 the adsorption of Cr^{+6} increases from 59.12% to 99.8% and 33.93% to 98.54% for NLP and NSD respectively. Thus results indicate that adsorption of Cr^{+6} favors in acidic media for the both cases.

Fig.5.: The influence of pH on removal of Chromium
 (Adsorbent : 1 g/l, Chromium: 10 mg/l, temp: 30° C)

4.4 Influence of temperature on adsorption

The influence of temperature on reduction of Cr^{+6} using NLP and NSD as adsorbents have been explained in the Fig. 6. The Figs indicate that the removal of Cr^{+6} favors at high temperature. Reduction of Cr^{+6} increases from 75% to 99.88% and 67.07% to 99.76% with the change of temperature from 304 K to 323 K for NLP and NSD respectively indicating that both sorption processes are endothermic in nature.

Fig 6.: Influence of Temperature on reduction of Cr^{+6}
 (Adsorbent : 1 g/l, Cr^{+6} : 10 mg/l, pH 1.35)

5.0 Adsorption isotherms

5.1 Langmuir adsorption isotherm

The rearranged Langmuir model equation (1) was used to correlate the experimental results obtained from the adsorption studies for elimination of Cr^{+6} using NLP and NSD as adsorbents at 303 K

$$\frac{C_e}{Q_e} = \frac{1}{Q^{\circ}K_L} + \frac{C_e}{Q^{\circ}} \quad (1)$$

where K_L and Q° are Langmuir constants related to the energy and the maximum adsorption capacity

of the activated NLP and NSD. The plot of C_e/Q_e vs. C_e is shown in Fig. 7. The linear plot with satisfactory regression coefficient of 0.993 and 0.998 suggest that these sorption processes follow the Langmuir isotherm satisfactorily. The optimum sorption capacities obtained for NLP and NSD were 55.87 mg/gm, and 40.0 mg/gm respectively.

Fig 7 : Langmuir isotherm of chromium removal by (a) NLP and (b) NSD
(adsorbent: 0.5 g/l, pH: 1.35, Temp: 30°C)

The separation factor (R_1) related to Langmuir isotherm was used to evaluate the viability of isotherms in these sorption process using both adsorbents. The values may be calculated using Eq. (2) [28].

$$R_1 = \frac{1}{(1+K_1C_0)} \quad (2)$$

Where C_0 (mg/l) was initial Cr^{+6} concentration and K_1 (l/mg) is Langmuir constant. The values of R_1 obtained for both adsorbents are within the range of 0.009 ($0 < R_1 < 1$), which indicates that the isotherms are highly favorable.

5.2 Freundlich isotherm

Applicability of the Freundlich isotherm for these sorption process have been find out satisfactorily using the following expression

$$\frac{X}{M} = Q_e = K_F \cdot (C_e)^{1/n} \quad (3)$$

$$\log\left(\frac{X}{M}\right) = \log K_F + \frac{1}{n} \log C_e \quad (4)$$

where Q_e is surface load in (mg/gm). The $\log(Q_e)$ vs $\log C_e$ has been plotted in Fig. 8. The values of n were 4.48 and 7.04 and K_F were 12.24 and 15.13 l/mg were obtained for adsorption with NLP and NSD respectively.

Fig 8 : Freundlich isotherm of chromium removal using (a) NLP and (b) NSD (adsorbent: 0.5 g/l, pH: 1.35, Temp: 30°C)

6.0 Adsorption Kinetics :

6.1 Lagergren pseudo first order kinetic model

The Pseudo First order kinetic model [25] has been taken to find out the applicability of the adsorption process with NLP and NSD as described in Eq. (5):

$$\frac{dQ_e}{dt} = k_1(Q_e - Q) \quad (5)$$

Where ' Q_e ' is the amount of Cr^{+6} adsorbed per unit mass of adsorbent NLP or NSD at equilibrium, and ' Q ' is the amount Cr^{+6} adsorbed on the adsorbent at any time ' t '. Here ' k_1 ' is the rate constant. From Eq. (5) the following Eq. (6) may be obtained :

$$\log(Q_e - Q) = \log Q_e - \frac{k_1 t}{2.303} \quad (6)$$

The values of $\log(Q_e - Q)$ versus ' t ' may be plotted at different temperature and applicability of this model may be determined easily.

6.2 Pseudo second order reaction kinetics

The experimental results were fitted in the Eq. (7) to find out the suitability of the Pseudo second order reaction model for these sorption processes

$$\frac{dQ_e}{dt} = k_2(Q_e - Q)^2 \quad (7)$$

Integrating the Eq. (7) and rearranging with boundary conditions at $t = 0$ to $t > 0$ and $Q = 0$ or > 0 the Eq. (8 & 9) may be obtained

$$\frac{t}{Q} = \frac{1}{(k_2 Q_e^2)} + \frac{t}{Q_e} \quad (8)$$

$$= \frac{1}{h} + \frac{t}{Q_e} \quad (9)$$

Here initial sorption rate is $h = (k_2 \cdot Q_e^2)$. The kinetics plot of t/Q vs. t at different concentrations plotted in the (Fig.9). The sorption rate ' h '(mg/gm-min) and ' k_2 '(g/gm-min) may be obtained from the Fig 9. The results of kinetic plots show that these processes follow pseudo second order reaction model better than the first order kinetic model.

Fig. 9: Pseudo Second Order Model for Cr⁺⁶ by NLP using (a) NLP and (b) NSD (adsorbent: 0.5 g/l, pH: 1.35, Temp: 30°C)

Conclusions:

Present studies confirmed the excellent potentiality of Indian Neem leaf powder (NLP) and Neem saw dust (NSD) for reduction of carcinogenic Cr⁺⁶ from industrial wastes. Results show that the Cr⁺⁶ reduction process is greatly dependent on toxicity of the solution. More than 99% removal of Cr⁺⁶ may be done for both adsorbent using 1.0 gm/l adsorbent at pH of 1.35 at 303 K from 10 mg/l solution. The sorption studies suggest that the maximum adsorption achieved by activated NLP and NSD were 55.86 and 40.0 mg/gm respectively. The kinetics studies suggest that both adsorption process followed second-order rate expression compared to first order kinetics. The linear plots from Freundlich's as well as Langmuir's model and the satisfactory values of correlation coefficients suggest the suitability of both adsorption process. Thus it can be concluded that NLP and NSD both have excellent potential for waste management but performance of NLP is better than NSD.

Acknowledgement

The characterization studies of the adsorbents were assisted by Shraddha Analytical Laboratory, Ghatkopar, Mumbai, India. Authors are grateful to Mr. Chandresh Dwivedi for his to analyze the adsorbents.

References :

- [1]. E. Daneshvar, M. J. Zarrinmehr, M. Kousha, A.M. Hashtjini, G.D.Saratale, A. Maiti, et al. *Technol.* 2019; 293(12) : 56–64.
- [2]. A.R. Asgari, F.Vaezi, S.Nasseri, O. Dördelmann, A.H. Mahvi, E.D.Fard. *Iran J Environ Heal Sci Eng.*2008;5(4):277–82.
- [3] S. Arris, M. B. Lehocine International Renewable Energy Congress IREC , March 25 -27, 2014.
- [4]. P. Venkateswarlu, M. V. Ratnam, D. S. Rao and M. V. Rao , *International Journal of Physical Sciences*, August 2007, Vol. 2 (8), pp. 188-195
- [5]. M.A. Barakat, *Arabian Journal of Chemistry*, 2010 , 4: 361-377.
- [6] J. Bayuo , *Jr. Environmental Health Science and Engineering*, (2021) 19:1193-1207.
- [7]. S. Singh, T. Alkal, Srivastava , S. K., R. Prakash , *International Journal of Research in Chemistry and Environment* Vol. 3 Issue 4 , October 2013 (61-67) ISSN 2248-9649.
- [8]. M. Smita, U.S. Honnannavar, *Journal of Environmental Science and Sustainability* (JESS), 2013, Vol. 1 (4): 120 – 123
- [9] S. Dhanakumar, G. Solaraj, R. Mohanraj, S. Pattabhi , *Indian Journal of Science and Technology*, (Dec. 2007)., Vol.1 No.2
- [10] M. Nur-E-Alam,, M.A.S. Mia, F. Ahmad , M. Mafizur Rahman, *Appl Water Sci.* 2018;8(5):1–7. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13201-018-0774-y>.
- [11] S. A. Anand , D.P. Nagarajappa , S. Sanjeev, S. Ramu, *International Journal of Innovative Research in Science, Engineering and Technology*, July 2014, Vol. 3, Issue 7.
- [12] S.H. Hasan, K.K. Singh, O. Prakash, M. Talat, *Journal of Hazardous Materials* , 2008, 152, 356–365.
- [13] Z A. Zakaria, M. Suratman, N. Mohammed, W.A. Ahmad , *Desalination* (2009), 244, 109–121.
- [14] R. Gayathri, M. Thirumarimurugan And T. Kannadasan , *International Journal Of Pharmaceutical and Chemical Sciences*, ISSN: 2277-5005
- [15] H. Krishna, A.V.V.S Swamy, *International Journal of Environmental Sciences and Research* Vol. 2, No. 1, 2012.119-125.
- [16] AH Tuama, A.A. Mohammed, A.H.Tuama, A.A. Mohammed , Scholars Research Library. *Euro J Appl EngSci Res.* 2014;3(2):19–32.35. Pan B, Pan B, Zhang W, Lv L, Zhang
- [17] S.] . Ba, K. Ennaciri, A. Yaacoubi , A. Alagui, A.Bacaoui, : *Iran J. Chem Eng.* 2018; 37(6) : 107–23.
- [18] VE. Pakade , T.D. Ntuli, A. E.Ofomaja, *Appl Water Sci.* 2017;7(6):3015–3030. doi: 10.1007/s13201-016-0412-5.
- [19] N. Nasseh, L. Taghavi , B. Barikbin, A R.Harifi-Mood. *J Water Reuse Desalin.* 2017;7(4):449–460. doi: 10.2166/wrd.2016.047.
- [20] T. Sathish, N.V.Vinithkumar, G. Dharani, R. Kirubakaran, *Appl Water Sci.* 2015; 5(2):153–160. doi: 10.1007/s13201-014-0174-x.
- [21] T. Dula, K. Siraj, S.A. Kitte, *ISRN Environ Chem.* 2014;1–9. doi: 10.1155/2014/438245
- [22] H.Sunil, KV Karthik, HN Pradeep,. *Int J Sci Res Publ.* 2014;4(1):2250–3153 Available: www.ijsrp.org.
- [23] C. K. Jain, D. S. Malik, , A. K. Yadav, *Environ. Process.* DOI 10.1007/s 40710-016-0143-5
- [24] B.V. Babu, S.Gupta , (2008) Adsorption of Cr(VI) using activated neem leaves: kinetic studies. *Adsorption* 14:85–92
- [25] R. Das, A. Mukherjee, I. Sinha, K. Roy and B. K. Dutta, *Int. J. Appl. Water Sci.* 10, pp-117, (2020)., <https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s13201-020-01184-5>
- [26] VO Arief, K. Trilestari, J. Sunarso, N. Indraswati, S. *Clean Soil Air Water*, (2008) , 36(12):937–962, Asgher M, Bhatti HN (2012) Evaluation
- [27] D. Kibami, C. Pongener, K.S. Rao1, D. Sinha, *Journal of Materials and Environmental Sciences.* (2017).8 (7), 2494-2505.
- [28] .A. Mullick,, S. Neogi,. The Royal Society of Chemistry (RSC Advances), (2016). 6, 65960-65975.

Prof. (Dr) Radharani Das, Dean (CHE, BT, FT) , Haldia Institute of Technology, West Bengal completed B.Tech, M.Tech, Ph.D in Chemical Engg. from University of Calcutta and Post Doc. from University of Torino, Italy . She published more than 80 papers in various national and international journals and conferences. Received Certificate of Merit award - 2008 & best paper award-2000 from Institute of Engineers India (IEI), Gold Medal from Calcutta University in 2010 and “**Teacher of the year Award**” from West Bengal University of Technology in 2017. She served as District Science

Advisor (Purba Midnapore) for Environment. She is associated with many international Journals as reviewer and contributed for two books on Environmental Science (WILEY-VCH) as co-author . She served as national council member of IChE during 2012 and 2015-2017, She was the founder secretary and vice-chairperson during 2010-2014 of Haldia Regional centre of IChE. She organised many national and international conferences including most prestigious Chemical Engg. congress the CHEMCON-17, ANS-2019 and Green Tech -22. She is actively engaged with various research work in the field of Ceramic Membranes, Environmental Science, Separation Process and Adsorption Process Technology .

Ms. Anima Das completed B.Tech in Chemical Engg from National Institute of Technology, Durgapur and M. Tech from Jadavpur University . She is engaged as lecturer in Chemical Engg. at Meghnath Saha Institute of Technology (MSIT), Haldia since 2003.

Ms. Ishita Sinha completed B. Tech. in Chemical Engg from Haldia Institute of Technology and M.B.A from ISWBM , University of Calcutta. She received B-Tech rank holder award in Chemical Engg of Maulana Abul Kalam Azad University from Governor of West Bengal. She received National level “**VIKAL AWARD**” for best paper presentation, from Indian Institute of Chemical Engineers (IICHE) , 2016, Best paper award from Student Chemical Engg. Congress of IChE, SCHEMCON '2015, MIT, Pune and Best Student Award' 2015 in Chemical Engg from HIT, Haldia. Presently she is associated with Linde Engg, a reputed MNC company as Dy. Manager for Project & Procurement section.